

Datum 2022-12-19
Dnr RAÄ-2022-2297

Handläggare: Kaj Thuresson

μ- XRF Instrument Report

Sample Identification Code

RAÄ Dnr RAÄ-2022-2297

Sample

Description of sample Metal buckle, 3 x 3 cm. Cylindrical with a domed cross on the top.

Age Migration era or later

Material Copper alloys with silver plating

Concentrations reference spectra from standards for comparison added.

Point of analysis

Three- or six-point measurements in close proximity to each other on each structural element of the buckle:

1. Inside the rim
2. Checkered pattern on the outside of the rim
3. Small plates on sides
4. Middle knob on top
5. Cross on top
6. Bord around buckle
7. Bord around buckle one more time
8. Checkered pattern on top
9. Square on cross ends
10. Wire around edge of buckle

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Purpose

Analysis performed in order to evaluate the material, composition of alloy, and where there are different areas of silver. The information is valuable when conservating the object and cleaning up original surfaces.

Method

No sample preparation was necessary, object was analysed as is. Three or six points were analysed at every spot and accumulated in the software in order to represent a mean value for the location. Two standards of silver copper alloys were measured for comparison.

Instrument Parameters

μ -XRF Artax 800, Mo X-ray tube with polycapillary lens, Bruker; Berlin, Germany

single point analysis (spot size <100 μ m)

line scan (lateral resolution <100 μ m)

elemental 2D mapping

quantification, MQuant Calib, Bruker; Berlin, Germany

quantification with standards

Voltage: 50 kV

Current: 600 μ A

Scan time per point: 10 sec

Number of measurement points: 33

Spot distance: na

Scan area: na

Total scan time: na

Filter no filter Al 315 μ m Mo 12.50 μ m other _____

Lens 0.060

Atmosphere air He for light element detection

Qualitative Results

1. Inside the rim: Accumulated spectra of three single point analysis. Mainly copper (Cu) and zinc (Zn). Small amounts of calcium (Ca), iron (Fe) and lead (Pb).

2. Checkered pattern on the outside of the rim: Accumulated spectra of three single point analysis. Mainly copper (Cu) and zinc (Zn). Small amounts of calcium (Ca), iron (Fe) and lead (Pb).

3. Small plates on sides: Accumulated spectra of three single point analysis. Mainly copper (Cu) and zinc (Zn). Small amounts of calcium (Ca), iron (Fe), lead (Pb) and tin (Sn).

4. Middle knob on top: Accumulated spectra of six single point analysis. Mainly copper (Cu) and zinc (Zn). Small amounts of calcium (Ca), iron (Fe) and lead (Pb).

5. Cross on top: Accumulated spectra of three single point analysis. Mainly copper (Cu) and zinc (Zn). Small amounts of calcium (Ca), iron (Fe) and lead (Pb).

6. Bord around buckle: Accumulated spectra of six single point analysis. Mainly Silver (Ag), less amount of copper (Cu) and zinc (Zn). Small amounts of calcium (Ca), iron (Fe) and lead (Pb).

7. Bord around buckle one more time: Accumulated spectra of six single point analysis. Mainly Silver (Ag), less amount of copper (Cu) and zinc (Zn). Small amounts of calcium (Ca), iron (Fe) and lead (Pb).

8. Checkered pattern on top: Accumulated spectra of three single point analysis. Mainly copper (Cu) and zinc (Zn). Small amounts of calcium (Ca), iron (Fe) and lead (Pb).

9. Square on cross ends: Accumulated spectra of three single point analysis. High amounts of Silver (Ag), copper (Cu) and zinc (Zn). Small amounts of calcium (Ca), iron (Fe) and lead (Pb).

10. Wire around edge of buckle: Accumulated spectra of three single point analysis. Mainly Silver (Ag), less amount of copper (Cu) and zinc (Zn). Small amounts of calcium (Ca), iron (Fe) and lead (Pb).

Quantitative Standards for reference

Standard: STD 5% Cu in Ag

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